

Effect of Intravenous Magnesium Sulphate in Duration of Blockade and Post Operative Pain Control for Spinal Anaesthesia in Lower Limb Surgeries

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Abstract:

Background: Since spinal anaesthesia provides efficient sensory and motor blockade with little side effects on the body, it is frequently utilised for lower limb procedures. Optimising postoperative pain management is still difficult, though. Because of its ability to inhibit calcium channels and NMDA receptors, intravenous magnesium sulphate has showed potential as an adjuvant to strengthen and extend analgesic effects. The study aimed to evaluate the impact of intravenous magnesium sulphate on the duration of blockade and postoperative pain control in patients undergoing lower limb surgeries under spinal anaesthesia.

Methods: 100 participants were randomly assigned to two groups: Group M (n=50) received 65mg/kg magnesium sulphate infusion in 250mL 5% dextrose, while Group N (n=50) received saline in 250mL 5% dextrose. Both groups received 3mL of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine for spinal anaesthesia. Hemodynamic parameters, duration of sensory and motor blockade, postoperative pain scores (VAS), and adverse effects were recorded and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The magnesium group showed significantly longer sensory (128.7 ± 12.5 min) and motor blockade (105.4 ± 11.3 min) durations compared to the control group (sensory: 104.5 ± 10.2 min; motor: 82.3 ± 9.8 min) ($p < 0.001$). Postoperative pain scores were consistently lower in Group M at all measured time points ($p < 0.05$). Hemodynamic stability and the incidence of adverse effects, including hypotension, bradycardia, nausea and shivering were comparable between groups ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: Intravenous magnesium sulphate significantly prolongs the duration of sensory and motor blockade and provides better postoperative pain control in lower limb surgeries under spinal anaesthesia without increasing adverse effects.

Recommendations: Intravenous magnesium sulphate can be considered as an effective adjuvant in spinal anaesthesia for enhancing blockade duration and improving postoperative pain management in lower limb surgeries.

Keywords: Magnesium sulphate, Spinal Anaesthesia, Postoperative Pain, Lower Limb Surgery, Sensory Blockade, Motor Blockade.

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Introduction

Spinal anaesthesia is a commonly employed anesthetic technique for lower limb surgeries due to its efficacy in providing profound sensory and motor blockade, along with minimal systemic effects. Despite its advantages, managing postoperative pain remains a challenge, necessitating the exploration of adjuvant therapies to enhance and prolong the analgesic effects of spinal anaesthesia. Intravenous magnesium sulphate

has emerged as a promising adjuvant due to its NMDA receptor antagonism and calcium channel blocking properties, which contribute to its analgesic and neuroprotective effects [1].

Magnesium is essential for several physiological functions, one of which is the regulation of nociceptive pathways. Magnesium can block the central sensitisation process, which is essential for the emergence and maintenance of chronic pain, by

antagonistically interacting with NMDA receptors. Magnesium's capacity to reduce the transmission of pain is further enhanced by its ability to inhibit calcium channels [2]. Studies have looked into the usage of magnesium sulphate in perioperative settings and have shown that it is effective in lowering opioid intake and postoperative pain.

The possible advantages of magnesium sulphate as an adjuvant in regional anaesthesia have been highlighted in recent research. Intravenous magnesium sulphate considerably lowers postoperative pain and opioid needs in patients undergoing various surgical operations, according to a comprehensive review and meta-analysis [3]. Similarly, research showed that magnesium sulphate improved postoperative analgesia in patients having orthopaedic procedures by extending the duration of sensory and motor blockade when used as an adjuvant to spinal anaesthesia [4].

Understanding the impact of magnesium sulphate on spinal anaesthesia outcomes is critical, given the growing emphasis on enhancing patient recovery and minimizing opioid consumption in the perioperative period. Effective postoperative pain management not only improves patient comfort but also facilitates early mobilization and reduces the risk of chronic pain development.

The study aims to evaluate the effect of intravenous magnesium sulphate on duration of blockade and post operative pain control for spinal anaesthesia in lower limb surgeries.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective, randomized, double-blind, controlled clinical trial.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period of 12 months (October 2022 to September 2023) at Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (IGIMS), Patna.

Participants: 100 patients, divided into two groups (50 patients each)

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged between 20 - 50 years
- Weight between 50-70 kgs
- Scheduled for lower limb surgery under spinal anaesthesia
- ASA physical status I & II

Exclusion Criteria

- Patient refusal
- Presence of comorbidities such as hypertension, diabetes
- Pregnant and lactating females
- Bleeding disorders
- Organ dysfunction, cardiac arrhythmia, congenital heart disease

- Mental retardation
- History of drug allergy to study drugs
- Known contraindications to spinal anaesthesia

Bias: To minimize bias, the study employed a double-blind design where neither the participants nor the investigators knew which group the participants were assigned to.

Data Collection: Data was collected on patient demographics, baseline vitals, hemodynamic parameters, adverse effects, and pain scores.

Procedure and Intervention Plan: Detailed pre-anesthetic checkup was conducted for all patients. All patients were NPO (nil per os) for 6 hours before surgery. Upon shifting to the operation theater (OT), basic standard monitors (ECG, SPO₂, NIBP) were attached and baseline vitals recorded. All patients were preloaded with 10ml/kg crystalloid before spinal anaesthesia.

Spinal Anaesthesia was administered under strict aseptic precautions. With the patients in the sitting position spinal anaesthesia was performed at the L3-L4 or L4-L5 level with a 25G Whitacre needle, and 3ml of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine was given. Group M (Magnesium Group): Received magnesium sulphate 65mg/kg infusion in 250mL 5% dextrose at a rate of 3.5 mL/min during the operation. Group N (Control Group): Received 30mL 0.9% sodium chloride in 250mL 5% dextrose infusion at a rate of 3.5 mL/min during the operation.

Patients were placed supine immediately after drug administration. Surgery commenced once the desired dermatome was anesthetized. All hemodynamic parameters were recorded every 5 minutes until skin closure.

Hypotension: Defined as a $\geq 20\%$ decrease from baseline systolic arterial pressure or SAP < 90 mmHg, treated with crystalloids (100mL) and inj. mephenteramine bolus (6mg) until baseline values were restored.

Bradycardia: Defined as a 30% drop in HR or ≤ 60 bpm, treated with IV atropine 0.5 mg.

Adverse Effects such as bradycardia, hypotension, nausea, vomiting, and shivering were noted and compared between groups.

Study Groups

- Group N (n=50): Received 0.5% Bupivacaine (3ml) + intravenous saline.
- Group M (n=50): Received 0.5% Bupivacaine (3ml) + intravenous Magnesium sulphate.

Statistical Analysis: All data was analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Statistical tests included the Student T-test and Chi-square test to compare the groups.

Result

A total of 100 patients were enrolled and completed the study, with 50 patients in each group. The

demographic characteristics, including age, weight, and ASA physical status, were comparable between the two groups (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Characteristic	Group N	Group M	p-value
Age (years)	35.4 ± 8.2	36.1 ± 7.9	0.678
Weight (kg)	63.2 ± 5.6	62.8 ± 5.4	0.749
ASA I	28 (56%)	27 (54%)	0.845
ASA II	22 (44%)	23 (46%)	0.845

Group M experienced a considerably longer mean duration of sensory blockade than Group N ($p < 0.001$). In a similar way, Group M also experienced a longer motor blockade duration ($p < 0.001$).

Table 2: Duration of Blockade

Blockade Type	Group N	Group M	p-value
Sensory Blockade (min)	104.5 ± 10.2	128.7 ± 12.5	<0.001
Motor Blockade (min)	82.3 ± 9.8	105.4 ± 11.3	<0.001

Postoperative pain scores were assessed using the VAS at 1, 2, 4, 6, and 12 hours post-surgery. Group M consistently showed lower pain scores compared to Group N, with statistically significant differences observed at all time points ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3: Postoperative Pain Scores (VAS)

Time (hours)	Group N	Group M	p-value
1	4.6 ± 0.8	3.2 ± 0.7	<0.001
2	4.8 ± 0.9	3.3 ± 0.8	<0.001
4	5.0 ± 0.9	3.5 ± 0.8	<0.001
6	5.2 ± 1.0	3.7 ± 0.9	<0.001
12	5.5 ± 1.0	3.9 ± 1.0	<0.001

Between the two groups, the incidence of bradycardia and hypotension was similar (Table 4). There were no appreciable variations in the need for atropine or vasopressor dosing.

Table 4: Hemodynamic Parameters and Adverse Effects

Parameter	Group N	Group M	p-value
Hypotension	8 (16%)	10 (20%)	0.607
Bradycardia	5 (10%)	6 (12%)	0.749
Nausea and Vomiting	4 (8%)	3 (6%)	0.695
Shivering	3 (6%)	2 (4%)	0.646

There were no statistically significant differences between the two groups in the occurrence of side effects, which included shivering, nausea, and vomiting ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion

The study included 100 patients divided into two groups of 50 each, with one group receiving intravenous magnesium sulphate (Group M) and the other receiving a saline (Group N) during lower limb surgeries under spinal anesthesia. The demographic characteristics, including age, weight, and ASA physical status, were comparable between the two groups, ensuring a balanced baseline for the comparison.

The results demonstrated a significant prolongation of both sensory and motor blockade durations in the magnesium group. Specifically, the mean duration of sensory blockade was 128.7 minutes in Group M compared to 104.5 minutes in Group N. Similarly, the motor blockade lasted 105.4 minutes in Group M versus 82.3 minutes in Group N. These

findings suggest that intravenous magnesium sulphate effectively extends the duration of anesthesia, potentially providing a more extended period of pain relief and reducing the need for additional anesthetic interventions during surgery.

Using the VAS, postoperative pain control was consistently better in the magnesium group at all time points tested (1, 2, 4, 6, and 12 hours after surgery). Group M's VAS values were considerably lower than Group N's, suggesting better pain control. For example, the mean VAS score in Group M was 3.2 after one hour after surgery, but it was 4.6 in Group N. This pattern persisted for the full 12-hour observation period, demonstrating the effectiveness of magnesium sulphate in managing pain following surgery.

The two group's haemodynamic stability, a crucial component of perioperative care, did not differ significantly. The frequency of bradycardia and hypotension was comparable, with 10% and 12% of patients in Group N and Group M, respectively, having bradycardia and 16% and 20% of patients in

Group N and Group M, respectively experiencing hypotension. Furthermore, the incidence of side effects such as shivering, nausea, and vomiting was low and similar in all groups, indicating that magnesium sulphate does not raise the risk of these issues.

Overall, giving intravenous magnesium sulphate to patients having lower limb procedures while under spinal anaesthesia improved postoperative pain control and lengthened the duration of sensory and motor blockade without raising the risk of side effects. These results provide credence to the magnesium sulphate's prospective usage as a useful anaesthetic adjuvant that improves patient comfort and lessens postoperative pain.

The effects of intravenous magnesium sulphate and ketorolac infusions on the duration of sensory and motor blocks, haemodynamic parameters, and postoperative analgesia under spinal anaesthesia were compared in a study. When compared to ketorolac, magnesium sulphate considerably decreased the need for postoperative analgesics and lengthened the period until the first rescue analgesia [5].

In spinal anaesthesia for lower limb procedures, three distinct dosages of magnesium sulphate (50 mg, 75 mg, and 100 mg) were combined with bupivacaine and fentanyl in a trial. The research discovered that, in comparison to the control group, all magnesium dosages increased the length of sensory and motor block. The 75 mg dosage, however, offered the optimum compromise between side effects and effectiveness [6].

Another study examined how patients having spinal anaesthesia for femur fracture surgery responded to a low dose of intravenous magnesium sulphate (5 mg/kg) in terms of sensory regression time. Without experiencing any serious side effects, the magnesium group demonstrated longer sensory regression times and lower postoperative opioid use [7].

According to a study, magnesium sulphate helped lower limb orthopaedic surgery patients to manage their pain better and require less postoperative opioids. The advantages of magnesium as a supplement to spinal anaesthesia were emphasised in the study [8]. Magnesium sulphate was reported to significantly relieve postoperative pain and decrease the prevalence of nausea and vomiting in paediatric patients with CNS tumours [9].

Conclusion

The study concluded that, without raising the risk of side effects, intravenous magnesium sulphate considerably extended the duration of sensory and

motor blockade and improved postoperative pain control when compared to the control group.

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